

////////////////////////////////////
**PRODUCT-INTEGRATED SUSTAINABLE ENERGY
TECHNOLOGIES - SIX YEARS OF EXPERIENCE WITH
INNOVATION AND SUSTAINABILITY**
////////////////////////////////////

Angèle Reinders ^{1, 2}, Juan de Borja ², André de Boer ¹

1) University of Twente, Faculty of CTW, P.O.Box 217, 7500 AE Enschede, The Netherlands.

2) Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering, Design for Sustainability, Landbergstraat 15, 2628 CE Delft, The Netherlands

E-mail: a.h.m.e.reinders@tudelft.nl, mdeborja@gmail.com, a.deboer@utwente.nl

ABSTRACT

Our paper shows the effects of different industrial design methods on 91 product concepts that have been developed during six design cases executed from 2005 until 2010 by students of Industrial Design Engineering in the Netherlands. It is shown that the application of 9 differently selected industrial design methods can yield innovative products with sustainable energy technologies that could be technically feasible. By an evaluation of the appreciation of the resulting product concepts it is found that the following three methods apparently are most beneficial: platform-driven product development, TRIZ and Design&Styling.

Keywords: Design for Sustainability, Design processes, Renewable Energy.

INTRODUCTION

The integration of renewable energy technologies and energy-saving technologies, such as solar photovoltaic technology, fuel cells and LEDs is very relevant to sustainable product design since it might lead to mass-produced consumer applications with these technologies. Though many options exist and technical issues can't be a major bottleneck, the application of integrated sustainable energy and energy-saving technologies has still not reached the level of common practice. For this reason from 2005 until 2010 six design cases [1-5] were executed on the application of sustainable technologies in products at the University of Twente in the Netherlands. In these cases special attention was paid to Industrial Design Methods (IDMs) that could potentially play a role in supporting innovative product development and yield interesting products with integrated sustainable energy technologies.

In our paper we assess the effect of IDMs on sustainable product design with integrated renewable energy technologies, as shown in Figure 1, by posing the following research question:

What is the effect of IDMs on the product development process with integrated renewable energy technologies?

To answer this question in this paper we will first describe the cases which have been executed from 2005 until 2010. Next we will present and shortly explain the IDMs applied. Subsequently the research method will be addressed and the resulting product concepts will be evaluated in relation to the IDMs applied, leading to our conclusions.

Figure 1. Urban furniture with PV powered artificial tree which emits LED light by Naeff and Stemkens (2010)

CASE DESCRIPTIONS

By the evaluation of six design cases that have been executed regarding the application of sustainable energy technologies in products we would like to investigate the effect of IDMS. The cases took place in subsequent years, from 2005 until 2010, in the framework of the course 'Sources of Innovation' of the Master of Industrial Design Engineering at University of Twente. In this course teams of two students designed in ten weeks an innovative product with one or more integrated technologies and a certain focus while using at least four out of nine IDMs. As such this design project resulted in one product concept per student team. Table 1 describes per case the energy technology involved, the focus of the design brief and the number of teams per case.

Year	Technology	Theme	Teams
2005	Fuel cell	Personal mobility [1]	17
2006	Fuel cell	Automotive applications [2]	15
2007	PV solar cells	Technology transfer [3]	17
2008	LEDs	Interaction and usability [4] [5]	24
2009	LEDs and PV	Self-sustaining products	20
2010	PV, LEDs and glass	Merging three technologies	17

Table 1. Cases in subsequent years of the course Sources of Innovation

In each case the design approach was based on a standard design process [6] - consisting of a clarification of the task, concept development and embodiment design - supported by industrial design methods that favor innovation in the design process, see Figure 2. Here we will shortly list them: Platform Driven Product Development -PDPD (a compulsory method since 2007), Innovation Phase Model - IPM, Technology Roadmapping - TRM, TRIZ, Lead User Study -LU, Innovative Design and Styling - IDS, Risk Diagnosing Methodology - RDM, Innovation Journey - IJ and Constructive Technology Assessment - CTA. Detailed descriptions of the methods are given by [1]; brief summaries are given in the next section. In Figure 3 the design process is shown of Figure 1.

DESIGN METHODS APPLIED

Platform-driven product development

A product platform defines a set of related products, a so-called product family that can be developed and produced in a time- and cost-efficient manner. Features of a product platform are modularity, connecting interfaces and common standards [7].

Innovation Phase Model

The innovation phase model aims to combine the intrinsic value of technology optimally with opportunities in the market. Divergence, selection and convergence of search fields related to technology and markets lead to innovative technology-product-market combinations [8].

Technology Roadmapping

A technology roadmap establishes a correlation between identified market needs and trends with existing and emerging technologies for a specific industry sector. Technology roadmaps usually cover 3 to 10 years and are used in strategic product planning, research planning and business planning [9].

TRIZ

TRIZ can be applied to estimate the probability of technology developments. TRIZ is a Russian acronym meaning Theory of Inventive Problem Solving. It is a comprehensive method based on long term patent research leading to certain basic rules - also called trends - governing problem solving in product development [10].

Lead User Study

Lead users are those who are the first to face needs that will eventually affect a larger market. By identifying and interviewing lead users, emerging market needs for a sustainable technology can be channeled into the development of innovative products [11].

Innovative Design and Styling

Design and styling is an asset for technological innovation. Cars, modern durables, and consumer products require a high degree of integration between functional and aesthetic aspects of design.

A market of products with integrated renewable energy technologies can be promoted by studying the image that potential users wish and designing products such that they meet those aesthetic requirements [12,13].

Risk Diagnosing Methodology

Companies must take risks to launch new products speedily and successfully. In this scope Risk Diagnosing Methodology aims to identify and evaluate technological, organizational and business risks in product innovation [14].

Innovation Journey

In the case of technology-based product design, product development often follows certain patterns. By examining the so-called innovation journeys of products in different fields, one may gain tools for assessing the potential innovation journeys of new products using emerging energy technologies [15].

Constructive Technology Assessment

New products must be promoted by manufacturers and retailers, must be approved by a competent authority in accordance with industry rules and standards, and must meet with acceptance from consumers. Constructive technology assessment focuses on these processes and how to improve them [16].

RESEARCH METHOD

We have explored the research questions by an evaluation of the marks given to the product concepts developed by the students. Namely, the grading of the course ‘Sources of Innovation’ distinguished between the quality of the application of IDMs and the feasibility and quality of the product concept. As such two two separate marks were available for every product concept, as well information about which IDMs were applied. This information was evaluated in a spread sheet. Based on these individual assessments, the following collective data of 91 product concepts executed in 6 subsequent cases was derived:

- Frequency of occurrences for each IDM for each case year and the total from 2005 to 2010
- The grading for the feasibility and quality of product concepts for each IDM and if it were not applied.
- Frequency at which each possible pair of IDMs was applied in projects - i.e. how often IJ and TRIZ, or Lead user studies and CTA, etc. were used together from 2005 to 2010
- The average concept grade for each of these 36 possible pairs of IDMs (2005 to 2010 total)

Figure 2. Linear design process in relation to innovation methods (brown squares) applied in this project

Figure 3. Design process related to product shown in Figure 1.

RESULTS REGARDING EFFECTS OF IDMs

Frequency of application of IDMs

Figure 4 shows the frequency of the application of IDMs for 91 product concepts developed in six cases from 2005 to 2010. PDPD has a dominant share of 83% since it became a compulsory method since 2007. IPM has been applied in 76% of the design projects, IDS in 61%. Other methods that have been applied up to a reasonable level are TRIZ (48%) and IJ (35%), followed by methods with a rather small share, namely TRM (28%), LU (25%), RDM (21%) and CTA (14%).

These are average values that can vary considerably per year. As an example in Figure 3 a comparison is drawn with the year 2006. In this year the share of PDPD was 86 % (out of 15 design projects), followed by LU and IDS with both a share of 67%. IPM was used in 53% of the design projects. In 2006 the methods TRIZ and TRM were jointly applied (40%).

Effect of IDMs on the quality of product concepts

Figure 5 shows the grading for the feasibility and quality of product concepts for each IDM and if it were and were not applied. It is found that the following three methods apparently are most beneficial: platform-driven product development, TRIZ and Design&Styling. According to this data the application of TRM seem to have a negative effect on the quality of the final product concept. This might be explained by the technological focus of this method.

Figure 4: Frequency of application of IDM's in the design projects executed by student teams in the six cases of 2005 until 2010 (blue bars) and in 2006 (red bars).

Figure 5: Grade for a product concept if a certain IDM is applied (blue bars) or if it is NOT applied (red bars) in the six cases executed in the period of 2005-2010 covering 91 design projects.

Effect of combination of IDMs

In addition to varying concept grades associated with the use of particular IDMs as illustrated in Figure 4, different pairings of IDMs also appear to be associated with variations in perceived concept quality (as represented by concept grades). It should be noted that some pairings occur infrequently which may distort results for those particular pairs. In Table 2 these pairs are indicated in red, whereas the pairs with the most frequent occurrence are indicated in green.

Next the average grade for the feasibility and quality for product concepts developed by applying a certain pair of IDMs was determined. These figures are shown in Table 3. Taking into account the likelihood that two IDMs could be paired, as indicated by the

green cells in Table 2, it can be concluded that the following combinations of IDMs tend to lead to a higher appreciation for a resulting product concept:

- 1) PDPD and IDS
- 2) IPM and IDS
- 3) IDS and TRIZ

As such we dare to conclude that Design&Styling apparently plays a key role in finding appropriate product applications for integrated renewable energy technologies and energy-saving technologies.

	PDPD	IPM	LU	IDS	RDM	TRIZ	TRM	IJ	CTA
PDPD		58	12	45	14	35	18	25	11
IPM			9	39	11	30	16	24	7
LU				9	1	4	3	4	-
IDS					6	19	11	14	10
RDM						8	4	5	2
TRIZ							12	13	4
TRM								6	-
IJ									2
CTA									

Table 2: Number of occurrences of pairs of IDMs in period of 2005-2010 covering 91 design projects. Green fields indicate the highest 30%, and red fields the lowest 30% of occurrences.

	PDPD	IPM	LU	IDS	RDM	TRIZ	TRM	IJ	CTA
PDPD		7,8	7,8	8,0	7,9	7,9	7,7	7,8	7,7
IPM			7,9	7,9	7,6	7,9	7,7	7,8	7,4
LU				7,9	7,0	8,3	7,2	8,1	n.a.
IDS					8,5	8,0	7,8	7,8	7,9
RDM						7,8	6,8	8,0	8,8
TRIZ							7,8	7,9	7,6
TRM								8,1	n.a.
IJ									7,0
CTA									

Table 3: Resulting grades for product concepts for the application of pairs of IDMs in period of 2005-2010 covering 91 design projects. Green fields indicate the highest 30%, and red fields the lowest 30% of grades.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

First we will discuss the research methodology. It would be possible that a slight dependence of the course coordinator's appreciation for certain IDMs or

product concepts could be introduced by using the marks of students. Also we are aware of the fact that a dependence exist regarding interrelated effects of IDMs since the grading happened for a combination of design methods and not for each IDM independently.

In general we conclude that the methods PDPD and IPM had a dominant share in the design projects, followed by IDS, TRIZ, and IJ. Methods with a rather small share are TRM, LU, RDM and CTA.

It is found that the following three methods apparently are most beneficial: PDPD, TRIZ and Design&Styling. According to our analysis the application of TRM seem to have a negative effect on the quality of the final product concept.

The following combinations of IDMs tend to lead to a higher appreciation for a resulting product concept: IDS and PDPD, or IPM, or TRIZ.

Seemingly Design&Styling plays a key role in finding appropriate product applications for integrated renewable energy technologies and energy-saving technologies. A possible explanation is that the utility and desirability and appeal of applications is not as easily apparent with new technologies as with established ones. Visually representing how these might function in an attractive manner can help bridge this gap, and among the IDMs Design&Styling is the most focused on form. While further study is required, this may highlight the importance of visual communication in making the case for sustainable energy products, or innovative products in general.

REFERENCES

- [1] Reinders, A.H.M.E. and Houten, F.J.A.M., *Industrial design methods for product integrated PEM fuel cells*, Oral presentation, Proceedings of NHA Annual Hydrogen Conference, Los Angeles, 2006.
- [2] Reinders, A., Boer, A. de, and Houten, F.J.A.M. van, *Innovative product design with PEM fuel cell technology for clean urban mobility*, Proceedings of European Hydrogen Energy Conference, 2007.
- [3] Reinders, A.H.M.E., *Product-integrated PV applications - How industrial design methods yield innovative PV-powered products*, Proceedings of 33rd IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, San Diego, 2008.
- [4] Reinders, A., Boer, A. de, Winter, A. de, and Haverlag, M., *Designing PV powered LED products - Sensing new opportunities for advanced technologies*, Proceedings of 34th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, Philadelphia 2009.
- [5] Reinders, A., Boer, A. de, Winter, A. de, Haverlag, M., *Designing PV powered LED products - Integration of PV technology*

in innovative products, Proceedings of 24th EU Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, Hamburg, 2009.

[6] Gerhard Pahl, Wolfgang Beitz, *Engineering Design*, London Design Council, 1984.

[7] Johannes I.M. Halman, Adrian P. Hofer, Wim van Vuuren: *Platform-Driven Development of Product Families: Linking Theory with Practice*, *Journal of Product Innovation Management* (20), 2003.

[8] Jan Buijs: *Modeling Product Innovation Processes, from Linear Logic to Circular Chaos*, *Creativity and innovation management*, June 2003.

[9] Robert Phaal, Clare Farrukh, David Probert, *Technology Roadmapping: Linking Technology Resources to Business Objectives*, University of Cambridge, 2001.

[10] Genrich Altshuller, *And Suddenly the Inventor Appeared*, Technical Innovation Centre, 1984.

[11] Eric von Hippel, *The Sources of Innovation*, Oxford University Press, 1988 and *Democratizing Innovation*, The MIT Press, 2005.

[12] TNO, *Design in the Creative Economy - A Summary*, Prensela Foundation, The Netherlands, 2005.

[13] Jens F. Christensen, *Asset Profiles for Technological Innovation*, *Research Policy* (24) 1995.

[14] Jimme A. Keizer, Johannes I.M. Halman, Michael Song: *From Experience, Applying the Risk Diagnosing Methodology*, *Journal of Product Innovation Management* (19), 2002.

[15] Arie Rip, *Technological Innovation - In Context*, Meeting of Lowlands Innovation Research Network, January 2003.

[16] Jasper Deuten, Arie Rip, Jaap Jelsma, *Societal Embedding and Product Creation Management*, *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management* (9), 1997.